

Denial and Negative Policing of Same-Sex Intimacy and Existence

Gopa Bhardwaj*

Denial of Sexual Diversity

Framing of same-sex intimacy as a perversion that flies in the face of religious morality still features prominently within contemporary homophobic discourse which reinforces the fear and prejudice that encourages homophobia and the victimisation of (Muholi, Zanele, 2009) *homophobia is not only publicly approved by society, but relies on unsubstantiated claims of a superficial and*

negatively imposed homosexual identity, contradictory ideas on morality, and the use of outdated laws. (Thabo Msiibi, 2014 a, b) This is the façade that conceals neo-conservatism and a resurgence of patriarchy, coated in the constructs of religion, nationalism, and law and emphasizes the rhetoric that

* **The author** is a Professor of Psychology in the School of Humanities & Social Sciences, Galgotias University, Uttar Pradesh, India.

promotes patriarchal conceptions of masculinity and enhances the conservative attitudes toward sexuality. This reinforces homophobic attitudes, encouraging the policing and oppression of already marginalised sexual identities that have traditionally been shrouded in secrecy.

There have been two different ways of dealing with homosexuality. The traditional approach finds ways of accommodating it and not talking about it, and there is the modern, ‘Western’ way, which searches for homosexuals – a public ‘gay’ identity. The strident assertion that heterosexuality is a natural norm often arises at moments of profound social, political and economic transformation. (Katz 1995; Rubin 2011) Labelling of same-sex intimacy as a perversion that is encouraged under the guise of religious morality still dominates within contemporary homophobic discourse. This assumption also creates a divide in the society and marginalizes the non-heterosexual. Society needs to not only understand the dynamics that prevail upon the lives of the LGTB but there also arises a need to change the attitude, emotions, thinking and behaviour of the decision makers along with the common person on the street.

One of the pioneer founders of the scientific study of sex, Magnus Hirschfeld, (1868-1935) a leading light in the field, conducted pioneering objective examinations of homosexuality, transvestism, and gender identity. His project was designed to provide a unified, comprehensive description of homosexuality, which, while ridding heterosexuals of gay prejudice also prompted homosexuals to confront their isolation and accept themselves. Magnus Hirschfeld was a German physician and sexologist and an outspoken advocate for sexual minorities. He founded the Scientific-Humanitarian Committee, which was defined by Historian Dustin Goltz, as the first advocacy group for homosexual and transgender rights. (From Wikipedia, the free encyclopaedia) His 1914 book ‘*Die Homosexualität des Mannes und des Weibes*’ (The Homosexuality of Men & Women) was a pioneering attempt to comprehensively survey homosexuality around the globe, in an effort to prove that homosexuality occurred in every culture. (Bauer, 2017).

The present paper analyses the state of sexual minorities, who are usually identified with reference to two distinct and complex characteristics: *sexual orientation* and *gender identity*. *Sexual orientation* is generally defined further as having at least three dimensions: *sexual self-identification, sexual behaviour, and sexual attraction or fantasy*. (Saewyc et al., 2004; Sell, 1997) *Gender identity* refers to a person’s internal sense of being masculine, feminine, or androgynous. In place of being a binary concept, gender identity includes gradations of masculinity to femininity and maleness to femaleness, as well as identification

as neither essentially male nor female. (Fausto-Sterling, 2000) Before the 1970s, scholars largely believed that sexual orientations, particularly homosexuality, were inherent dispositions that entail universal categories. The Gay/lesbian subculture began to bloom throughout the 1970s, and this movement saw the beginning of a new era and a general orientation toward identity-building and cultural change.

Foucault's writings on sexuality (e.g., 1978; 1990) greatly influenced scholars in the 1980s and 1990s to defend group identities, including homosexuality, as socially constructed phenomena. (e.g., Bersani, 1995; Butler, 1990; Halperin, 1990; Rubin, 1984) As Berg-Sørensen, Holtug, and Lippert-Rasmussen (2010) stated "It has become common to distinguish between essentialist and constructivist understandings of group identities, such as gender, race, and culture." However, this discursive space is full of problems in the social sciences, and so is the case for homosexuality, as there is also the controversial question of whether homosexuality is innate or socially constructed. Some scholars in the West, such as Ball (2001) and Halwani (1998), defended homosexuality from an essentialist approach.

However, Kugle and Hunt (2012) maintained that gender and sexuality studies in the West have been dominated by the 'queer theory' which builds on both, feminist challenges to the idea that gender is a part of the essential self and emphasizes on close examination of the socially constructed nature of sexual acts and identities. On the other hand, gay/lesbian studies from the essentialist view points, inquired into natural and unnatural behaviour with respect to homosexual behaviour. Queer theory under the influence of post-modernism; expands its focus to encompass any kind of sexual activity or identity that falls into normative and deviant categories and considers all group identities as socially constructed. (Alipour 2017).

Researchers, over the years, have tended to define sexual orientation by either, *sexual orientation* or/and *gender identity*. The criterion is either self-identification as gay/lesbian, bisexual or heterosexual, or the gender of one's sexual partners (same sex, both same and opposite sex, or opposite sex), Transgender has been used as an umbrella term to describe people with gender identities, expressions or behaviours which differ from their biological sex at birth. (Feinberg, 1992; Kirk & Kulkarni, 2006) Although the term 'transgender' is commonly used and often synonymously with transsexual, the latter is more generally used as a sub-set of transgender individuals who undergo gender reassignment surgery and/or hormone treatment to align physical sex and gender identity.

In the present era terms such as “gender queer” are often used by younger transgender people, as well as those people, who do not identify as transgender, to describe a wide range of gender identifications, behaviours and expressions different from being exclusively male or female. (Nestle, Howell & Wilchins, 2002) As with sexual orientation, gender identity is not an entirely fixed characteristic, and many transgender people move fluidly between identities over time, often without any specific labels. (Whittle, Turner, & Al-Alami, 2007) Sexual orientation varies among transgender individuals, just as it does among people who perceive their gender identity to be aligned with their biological sex. However, no definite conclusion can be drawn as there is a dearth of research and authentic data in this field.

The Problems

Social stigma, prejudice and discrimination has been associated with minority sexual orientation, (Cochran, Mays & Sullivan, 2003; de Graaf et al., 2006; King et al., 2008; Mays & Cochran, 2001; McCabe, Bostwick, Hughes, West, & Boyd, 2010) that LGBT people suffer from discrimination across their lifespan, in the form of personal rejection, hostility, harassment, bullying, and physical violence. (D’Augelli, Grossman, Salter, et al., 2005; D’Augelli, Hershberger, & Pilkington, 2001; Ryan, Huebner, Diaz, and Sanchez, 2009) *Institutional discrimination* occurs due to legal bases and public policies that create inequities or fail to provide requisite protection against the sexual orientation-based discrimination.

The nuances of socialization among the intersexual, cry out for more sophisticated analysis vision of sexual multiplicity to be realized. The first openly intersexual children and their parents will have to be brave pioneers who will bear the brunt of society’s growing pains. The future, though, it could take generations to achieve – the prize, as such, might be a society in which sexuality is multidimensional and exists in multiple domains and something to be celebrated for its subtleties; and not something to be feared or ridiculed. No doubt, the most troublesome arena by far would be the rearing of such children. Parents, at least since the Victorian era, have fretted, sometimes to the point of outright denial, over the fact that their children are sexual beings and have existential value.

The prevailing binary system of physical and psychological existence cannot and should not continue. Today’s society cannot just continue with the assumption that there are only two types of normal body and two types of sex. There is not only a need to give a voice to intersex people and how they experience intersexuality, but also to highlight how various social and legal

structures have provided services in a way that exclude such people and deny their existential reality. Society approves the control of intersexual bodies because they blur and bridge the great divide. Moreover, there seems to be a cultural requirement to maintain this clear distinction between the sexes to justify the denial of justice to those who do not fall within the binary classification. Culture in most of the world is deeply entrenched in the idea that there are only two sexes, even language refuses other possibilities.

Analysing the Greek origin of the word *hermaphrodite*, we find that it originates from the Greek name Hermes, variously known as the messenger of the gods, the patron of music, the controller of dreams or the protector of livestock, and Aphrodite, the goddess of sexual love and beauty. According to Greek mythology, those two gods parented ‘Hermaphroditus’, who at age fifteen became half male and half female, when his body fused with the body of a nymph he fell in love with. In some true hermaphrodites, the testis and the ovary grow separately but bilaterally, in others they grow together within the same organ, forming an ovo-testis. Not infrequently, at least one of the gonads functions quite well, producing either sperm cells or eggs, as well as functional levels of the sex hormones – androgens or oestrogens. Although in theory, it might be possible for a true hermaphrodite to become both father and mother to a child, in practice the appropriate ducts and tubes are not configured, so that the egg and the sperm can actually meet. But if the state and the legal system have an interest in maintaining a two-party sexual system, they are defying nature. For, biologically speaking, there are many gradations running from female to male; and depending on how one calls the shots, one can argue that along that spectrum lie at least five sexes—and perhaps even more. (Fausto-Sterling, 2000).

The Netherlands is one of the first countries to implement a public policy on homosexuality to promote and legalize the social acceptance of gays/lesbians. Government has taken several measures like strengthening the gay/lesbian movement; protecting gay/lesbian rights and interests in international relations. The Government promotes research, registration, and heavily prosecute anti-gay/lesbian violence and verbal discrimination. They allow foreign partners to be entitled to a residence permit; include homosexuality in sexual education; promote gay/lesbian studies at the university level; make inheritance possible for non-married couples; include gay/lesbian themes in state-sponsored media; and fight heterosexism. (Davidson, 2018).

Feminist post-structuralist theory has analysed how power works by not only forcing people ‘into particular ways of being’, but by making those ways

‘desirable’ so that people adopt them as their own. (Davies & Gannon, 2005, p. 318) We are all on a gender continuum and there exists a societal pressure to be ‘either male or female’, particularly reinforced during childhood, which can be labelled as ‘a patriarchal sovereignty’ established through ‘violence and transgression, voyeurism, pleasure, and pride.’ The ‘heterosexual men’ assume the role of the rightful bearers of authority over others. Regarding the gender system, many people only acknowledge the categories of male and female, which further make it difficult for them to understand gender fluidity.

The Indian epic Mahabharata mentions the character of ‘Shikhandi’ as a transgender person; however, this state has been rationalized with a purpose, i.e. a vendetta arising from refusal in love and marriage in an earlier birth of the woman ‘Amba’. This refusal, in turn, was due to the action taken by ‘Bhishma Pitamah’ who abducted her with her sisters for an alliance of marriage to his younger brother and thus polluting her existential value. There is not much opinion expressed in the Hindu religion about LGBT. In the Mahabharata only, we come to know about ‘Chitrangada’, a princess from Manipur who was a girl, but was brought up as a boy, and married Arjuna and had a son by him. Again, this behaviour takes on a shade of pseudo-rationalism, that if the king had an only daughter, then she had to be brought up as a son. The entire discourse focuses on administrative strategies and pays little attention to the female existence and associated characteristics. The literature by some feminist authors has depicted homosexuality in short stories like ‘Lihaaf’ (Ismat Chutai) but they were not appreciated in the public domain. There is a permanent façade of secrecy and fear on such types of writings. On the positive side, the notion of ‘Shiva’ as ‘Ardha Narishwar’ depicts the equal depiction of the male and the female existence. However, the portrayal of ‘Parvati’ – ‘Shiva’s wife on the left side indicates both the power as well as emotions, since the heart, also on the left side of the body is predominantly linked to emotions, which may carry a sense of weakness and vulnerability.

A View from Islamic Perspective

Muslim revisionist scholars who study sexual diversity in Islam, in particular homosexuality, have used an essentialist epistemology to explain a more tolerant approach towards Islam and same-sex desires and acts, claiming that the Western “academic debate has moved far away from the practical concerns of activists, legal experts, and religious leaders.” (Kugle & Hunt, 2012, p. 261) Although one cannot ignore the political, cultural, and social context that influenced these scholars to choose an essentialist approach to same-sex desires and acts, (and, in their words, homosexuality) however, the driving force is more of a

theological-ethical reasoning from ‘Quranic verses’, such as 49:13, 42: 8, 11: 118–119, 30: 22. According to modern commentators of the ‘Qur’an’, (El Fadl, 2002) these verses show that the diversity among human beings is a part and parcel of the world that God created. Relying on this interpretation, scholars, such as ‘Kugle’, have argued that since the ‘Qur’an’ accepts diversity as part of God’s creative will, therefore, if same-sex desires and acts are part of that diversity, they are, indeed, accepted by the ‘Qur’an’.

According to ‘Alipour’, (2017) *essentialism*, however, has different meanings for different scholars. (Phillips, 2010) For Muslim scholars, an essentialist approach to homosexuality leads to interpretation ranging from “God’s creation” to “biological variation” and “early childhood experiences”. (Kugle, 2010, p. 2) The common point that all these three categories share in common is that homosexuality does not occur through rational choice. Muslim scholars who defend same-sex desires and acts from an essentialist approach limit their argument to homosexuality and do not include other manifestations of same-sex sexuality, such as bisexuality. They, therefore assume that bisexuality does not fall under the diversity that the ‘Qur’an’ talks about. For instance, ‘Kugle claimed bisexuality seems to be an excluded feature from the “Qur’an-based argument” because the ‘Qur’an’ does not observe it as a part of a diverse creation and/or an innate disposition. (Kugle, 2010, p. 10).

However, it is again not explained why bisexuality is not a part of God’s creation. Moreover, scientific research (Diamond, 1998; Rosenthal, Sylva, Safron, & Bailey, 2011) leans toward the conclusion that bisexuality is related largely to genetic inheritance or early childhood experiences. Therefore, it can be concluded that if the strategy of “just created that way” or essentialism work in the Islamic context at all, it can be applied to bisexuality as well and relate to diversity too. ‘Alipour’ (2017), however, puts an argument against an essentialist approach, citing that the essentialist approach is based on a three pronged view of homosexuality: lifestyle, desire, and act or practice. Therefore, it becomes imperative to explain to what extent homosexuality is God’s creation, which the essentialist scholars have failed to pay any attention to.

Psychological Problems and Issues

Legal restrictions on same-sex relationships, hate crimes against gays and lesbians, bullying of gay teens, and familial and social rejection of homosexuals are examples of heterosexism that denigrate and devalue non-heterosexual forms of identities, behaviours, relationships, and communities. This is also known as Internalized *homonegativity* (IH) which refers to the process, whereby lesbian, gay, and bisexual (LGB) persons themselves internalize societal messages toward

gender and sex—often unconsciously—as part of their self-image (Meyer, 1995). Herek (2000) argued that this incorporation can result in negative feelings toward oneself when a person recognizes his or her own homosexuality or bisexuality. The negative internalized beliefs generate a psychological dilemma between romantic desires and negative beliefs about the self; the disjuncture raises the feelings of guilt and shame, low self-esteem, and other emotional difficulties (Herek, 2007; Malyon, 1982; Meyer & Dean, 1998; Shidlo, 1994; Weinberg, 1973).

Herek (1994, 1995, 2004) however, has criticized conceptualizations of IH that are focused too narrowly on fear and avoidance of LGBT persons and enforced by a clinical language that discriminates, pathologizes and stigmatizes particular identities and attitudes. Herek (2004) is of the opinion that research has failed to detect fear and anxiety responses when heterosexuals view photographs of men having sex with men. Instead, disgust and anger appear to be central to heterosexual people's negative responses and attitudes to LGBT persons. It is important to recognize, as Hudson and Ricketts (1980), Mayfield (2001) and Szymanski and Carr (2008) have emphasized that internalized *homonegativity* (IH) is affected by wider societal factors and is not simply a product of personal, subjective, and “irrational” fears. Russell and Bohan (2006) and Herek (2007) have emphasized that IH is not an inherent personal response from individuals but a product of social and political stigma and bias.

Rigmore, Heather, Munthe-Kaas and Michael W. Ross (2016) found that there is a growing empirical support for a relationship between experiencing IH (internalized homophobia) and higher levels of psychological distress, with the minority stress model serving as a useful framework for explaining such effects, as well as negative mental health, through lower self-esteem and perception of a reduced availability of social support. Primary and secondary research is needed to elucidate these connections.

An added issue along with LGBT is the notion of being asexual. (Gupta 2017) ‘Asexual’ refers to the stigmatization or invisibility of non-sexuality. We need to understand this issue also, because the relationship between contemporary asexual lives and compulsory sexuality, or the ‘privileging’ of sexuality and the ‘marginalizing’ of non-sexuality has been ignored in societal life and very little attention has been paid to the existence and trauma of being asexual and forced to live a traumatic life in order to be “normal”. According to Gupta, asexuality refers to de-emphasizing the importance of sexuality in human life; developing new types of nonsexual relationships; constituting asexuality as a sexual orientation or identity; and engaging in community building and

outreach. Gupta (2017) argues that some of these practices offer only a limited disruption of compulsory sexuality, but some of these practices pose a radical challenge to sexual norms by calling into question the widespread assumption that sexuality is a necessary part of human flourish, emphasizing the concept of compulsory sexuality.

Another proclaimed malady in this context is *GID (Gender Identity Disorder)*. GID is dependent on two components: *first*, in adults, strong and persistent cross-gender identification; and in children, various behaviours like the insistence that they are the opposite sex, a preference for cross-dressing, and a preference for playmates of the opposite sex. The *second* component involves persistent discomfort with his or her sex or a sense of inappropriateness in the gender role of that sex. Various studies have tried to document the prevalence of the disorder, but there is no consensus on this issue. (Bakker, van Kesteren, Gooren, & Bezemer, 1993; De Cuypere et al., 2007; Wilson, Sharp, & Carr, 1999).

Furnham & Sen (2013) talk about the lay theories, which are “the informal, ‘common sense’ explanations that people provide for particular social behaviours, and they often differ significantly from ‘scientific’ explanations and theories”. (Furnham, 1988, p. 6) No lay theory research has been carried out in relation to gender identity disorder (GID). There is an interesting and extensive literature on cultural and individual differences of correlates of attitudes toward gender. (Jayaratne & Anderson, 2001; Knox, Zusman, & McNeeley, 2004; Mahalingham, 2003, 2007a, 2007b; Quinn & Luttrell, 2004; Ridgeway & Correll, 2004; Tucker & Keil, 2001) These studies have not only identified consistent race and cultural differences, but also class, caste, and gender differences, in beliefs about the origins of gender (as opposed to sex). Findings suggest a significant, largely unaddressed public health problem among the LGBT people. (King et al., 2008).

However, little is known about the specific risk and protective factors in particular subgroups of the LGBT population. Findings of an earlier large-scale Australian survey, (Jorm et al., 2002) confirmed that bisexual behaviour and identity were strongly associated with an elevated risk of mood and anxiety disorders in both men and women. Similar to men who identified as gay or bisexual, men who reported being unsure about their sexual identity were significantly more likely to have mood or anxiety disorders than heterosexual men. In women, however, rates of these disorders were generally not significantly higher than heterosexual women.

Among some urban men who have sex with men, elevated risk of HIV/AIDS has been found to be associated with depression, substance abuse, and

elevated risk of suicidal behaviour. (Paul et al., 2002; Stall, et al, 2003) Among the most pressing questions for future research is whether LGBT people are over-represented among suicide deaths, and if so, why? Given the stigma and secrecy associated with minority sexual orientation and gender identity, psychological methods appear to have limited utility for this purpose. (King et al. 2008).

Overall, however, there is a dearth of mental health interventions specifically designed for LGBT community, and as a consequence, a large majority of those who need treatment must rely on general community providers. However, in recent years, there has been growing recognition of the need to include more extensive information on the LGBT community in educational and training programs for mental health professionals.

What Can Be Done

- Encourage inclusion of measures of sexual orientation and gender identity and partnership status in all suicide and mental health research, including clinical, neurobiological and genetic studies, along with appropriate safeguards for privacy and confidentiality.
- Educate key stakeholders like funding agencies, researchers, institutional review boards etc., regarding the need for questions on sexual orientation and gender identity in suicide and mental health research.
- Develop and carry longitudinal studies, using large cohort designs to ensure sufficient numbers of the LGBT community.
- Organise campaigns to reduce the superstitious beliefs, particularly about mood and anxiety disorders, among the LGBT community and encourage development of equitable, accessible, and culturally appropriate mental health as well as substance abuse services for the LGBT community from all segments of society.
- Create awareness among the LGBT community about the cause and effect relationship between mood, anxiety, and substance use disorders further extending to suicides.
- Create programmes to encourage the help seeking from the LGBT community, suffering from mental disorders, or those who are suicidal; and put in place the much-needed mental health, interventions and programs required by the LGBT community.
- Develop programs for early identification of risk behaviours and mental health disorders and substance abuse, especially among the LGBT youth.

- Adaptations of mental health interventions and therapies of the LGBT community have been established to be effective among the general population
- Create LGBT-specific behavioural health interventions, (related in particular to substance abuse) and ensure the involvement of the people of the LGBT community of all ages, racial and ethnic groups, and gender identity constituencies in the planning, design, development, and implementation of all new mental health interventions and programs for substance abuse treatment.

As a concluding remark, one can only say that this is a much-needed arena for research and intervention. I have been able to provide only a glimpse of the issues, but they are all highly significant in the current scenario. And most importantly, there is a need to articulate powerful and creative expressions that fight the silence, erase the marginalisation of these people and bring them to the main stream of the society with honour, dignity and self-worth.

References

1. M. Alipour, "Essentialism and Islamic Theology of Homosexuality: A Critical Reflection on an Essentialist Epistemology toward Same-Sex Desires and Acts in Islam", *Journal of Homosexuality*, 64:14, 2017, pp. 1930-1942.
2. Bakker, P. van Kesteren, L. Gooren, and R. Bezemer, "The prevalence of transsexualism in the Netherlands", *Acta Psychiatrica Scandinavica*, 87, 1993, pp. 237-238.
3. Ball, "Essentialism and universalism in gay rights philosophy: Liberalism meets queer theory", *Law and Social Inquiry*, 26, 2001, pp. 271-293.
4. Heike Bauer Bauer, *The Hirschfeld Archives: Violence, Death, and Modern Queer Culture*, Philadelphia, USA: Temple University Press, 2017.
5. Berg-Sørensen, N. Holtug, and K. Lippert-Rasmussen, "Essentialism vs. constructivism: Introduction", *Distinction: Scandinavian Journal of Social Theory*, 11, 2010, pp. 39-45.
6. L. Bersani, *Homos*, Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press, 1995.
7. J. Butler, *Gender trouble: Feminism and the Subversion of Identity*, New York, NY: Routledge, 1990.
8. S.D. Cochran, V.M. Mays, and J.G. Sullivan, "Prevalence of mental disorders, psychological distress and mental health services use among lesbian, gay and bisexual adults in the United States", *Journal of Consulting and Clinical Psychology*, 71(1), 2003, pp. 53-61.
9. R. J. Davidson, "Strategic trade-offs: Movement-government interactions and Dutch gay and lesbian policy, 1986-1994", *Mobilization: An International Quarterly*, 23(2), 2018, pp. 203-218.
10. D'Augelli, A. R., Grossman, A. H., Salter, N. P., Vasey, J. J., Starks, M. T., & Sinclair, K. O. (2005). Predicting the suicide attempts of lesbian, gay, and bisexual youth. *Suicide and Life-Threatening Behavior*, 35(6), 646-660.
11. D'Augelli, S.L. Hershberger, and N.W. Pilkington, "Suicidality patterns and sexual orientation-related factors among lesbian, gay, and bisexual youths", *Suicide and Life-Threatening Behavior*, 31, 2001, pp. 250-264.

12. G. De Cuypere, M. van Hemelrijck, A. Michel, B. Carael, G. Heylens, R. Rubens, S. Monstrey, "Prevalence and demography of trans-sexualism in Belgium", *European Psychiatry*, 22, 2007, pp. 137–141.
13. R. De Graaf, T.G. Sandfort, and M. ten Have, "Suicidality and sexual orientation: Differences between men and women in a general population-based sample from the Netherlands", *Archives of Sexual Behavior*, 35(3), 2006, pp. 253–262.
14. M. Diamond, "Bisexuality: A biological perspective" in E. J. Haeberle and R. Gindorf (Eds.), *Bisexualities: The ideology and practice of sexual contact with both men and women*, New York, 1998, pp. 53–80.
15. K. El Fadl, *The Place of Tolerance in Islam*, Boston, MA: Beacon Press, 2002.
16. Fausto-Sterling, *Sexing the Body: Gender Politics and the Construction of Sexuality*, New York: Basic Books, 2000.
17. M. Foucault, *The History of Sexuality* (vol. 1), New York, NY: Vintage Books, 1978.
18. A Furnham and R. Sen, "Lay Theories of Gender Identity Disorder", *Journal of Homosexuality*, 60:10, 2013, pp. 1434-1449.
19. M. King, et al. "A systematic review of mental disorder, suicide, and deliberate self-harm in lesbian, gay, and bisexual people", *BMC Psychiatry*, 8: 70, 2008. Retrieved June 8, 2009, from <http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC2533652/>
20. S.C. Kirk, and C. Kulkarni, "The whole person: A paradigm for integrating the mental and physical health of trans clients", in M.D. Shankle (Ed.), *The handbook of lesbian, gay, bisexual and transgender public health: A practitioner's guide to service*, New York: Harrington Park Place 2006, pp. 145–174.
21. L. Feinberg, *Transgender Liberation: A Movement Whose Time Has Come*, New York: World View Forum, 1992.
22. K Gupta, "And Now I'm Just Different, but There's Nothing Actually Wrong With Me: Asexual Marginalization and Resistance", *Journal of Homosexuality*, 64: 8, 2017, pp. 991-1013.
23. S. Habib, "Queer-friendly Islamic hermeneutics", *In Islam Review*, 21, 2008, 32–33.
24. S. Habib, *Islam and Homosexuality*, Santa Barbara, CA: Praeger, 2010.
25. Halperin, *One Hundred Years of Homosexuality*, New York, NY: Routledge, 1990.
26. R. Halwani, "Essentialism, Social Constructionism, and the History of Homosexuality", *Journal of Homosexuality*, 35(1), 1998, pp. 25–51.
27. G.M. Herek, "Assessing heterosexuals' attitudes toward lesbian and gay men: A review of empirical research with the ATLG scale", in B. Greene & G. M. Herek (Eds.), *Lesbian and Gay Psychology: Theory, Research and Clinical Applications*, Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage, 1994, pp. 206–228.
28. G.M. Herek, "Psychological Heterosexism in the United States" in A. D'Augelli and C. Patterson (Eds.), *Lesbian, Gay and Bisexual Identities over the Lifespan: Psychological Perspectives*, Oxford, UK: Oxford University Press, 1995, pp. 321–346.
29. G.M. Herek, "The Psychology of Sexual Prejudice", *Current Directions in Psychological Science*, 9(1), 2000, pp: 19–22.
30. G. M. Herek, "Beyond 'homophobia': Thinking about sexual prejudice and stigma in the twenty-first century", *Sexuality Research and Social Policy*, 1(2), 2004, pp. 6–24.
31. G.M. Herek, "Confronting sexual stigma and prejudice: Theory and practice", *Journal of Social Issues*, 63(4), 2007, pp. 905–925.
32. W.W. Hudson, and W.A. Ricketts, "A strategy for the Measurement of Homophobia", *Journal of Homosexuality*, 5, 1980, pp. 357–372.

33. T.E. Jayaratne, and E. Anderson, "Beliefs about the genetic origins of gender, class, race differences", *Journal of Law, Medicine and Ethics*, 29, 2001, pp. 40–50.
34. F. Jorm, A. E. Korten, B. Rodgers, P. A. Jacomb, and H. Christensen, "Sexual orientation and mental health: Results from a community survey of young and middle-aged adults", *British Journal of Psychiatry*, 180, 2002, pp. 423–427.
35. Jonathan Katz, *The Invention of Heterosexuality*, New York: Dutton, 1995
36. M. King, J. Semlyen, S.S. Tai, H. Killaspy, D. Osborn, D. Popelyuk, "A systematic review of mental disorder, suicide, and deliberate self-harm in lesbian, gay, and bisexual people", *BMC Psychiatry*, 8: 70, 2008. Retrieved on 8 June 2009 from <http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC2533652/>.
37. Knox, M. Zusman, and A. McNeeley, "Beliefs about Men: Gender Differences among College Students", *College Student Journal*, 38, 2004, pp. 633–636.
38. S.C. Kirk, and C. Kulkarni, "The whole person: A paradigm for integrating the mental and physical health of trans clients" in M. D. Shankle (Ed.), *The handbook of lesbian, gay, bisexual and transgender public health: A practitioner's guide to service*, New York: Harrington Park Place, 2006, pp. 145–174.
39. S. Kugle, *Homosexuality in Islam: Critical Reflection on Gay, Lesbian, and Transgender Muslims*, Oxford, England: One world Publications, 2010.
40. S. Kugle and S. Hunt, "Masculinity, homosexuality and the defense of Islam: A case study of Yusuf al-Qaradawi's media fatwa", *Religion and Gender*, 2, 2012, pp. 254–279.
41. R. Mahalingham, "Essentialism, culture and beliefs about gender among the Aranvanis of Tamil Nadu, India", *Sex Roles*, 49, 2003, pp. 489–496.
42. R. Mahalingham, "Beliefs about chastity, machismo and caste identity: A culture psychology of gender", *Sex Roles*, 56, 2007a, pp. 239–249.
43. R. Mahalingham, "Culture, ecology and beliefs about gender in son preference caste groups", *Evolution and Human Behaviour*, 28, 2007b, pp. 319–329.
44. A.K. Malyon, "Psychotherapeutic implications of internalized homophobia in gay men", *Journal of Homosexuality*, 7(2–3), 1982, pp. 59–69.
45. W. Mayfield, "The development of an internalized homonegativity inventory for gay men", *Journal of Homosexuality*, 41(2), 2001, pp. 53–76.
46. V. M. Mays, and S.D. Cochran, "Mental health correlates of perceived discrimination among lesbian, gay and bisexual adults in the United States", *American Journal of Public Health*, 91(11), 2001, pp. 1869–1876.
47. S. E. McCabe, W.B. Bostwick, T.L. Hughes, B.T. West, and C.J. Boyd, "The relationship between discrimination and substance use disorders among lesbian, gay and bisexual adults in the United States", *American Journal of Public Health*, 100(10), 2010, pp. 1946–1952.
48. I.H. Meyer, "Minority stress and mental health in gay men", *Journal of Health and Social Behavior*, 36(1), 1995, pp. 38–56.
49. H. Meyer, "Prejudice, social stress, and mental health in lesbian, gay, and bisexual populations: Conceptual issues and research evidence", *Psychological Bulletin*, 129, 2003, pp. 674–697.
50. I.H. Meyer, "Prejudice and discrimination as social stressors" in I.H. Meyer and M. E. Northridge (Eds.), *The health of sexual minorities*, New York, NY: Springer, 2007, pp. 242–267.
51. I.H. Meyer and L. Dean, "Internalized homophobia, intimacy, and sexual behaviour among gay and bisexual men", in G.M. Herek (Ed.), *Stigma and sexual orientation: Understanding prejudice against lesbians, gay men, and bisexuals*, Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage, 1998, pp. 160–186.

52. Zanele Muholi, *Mapping Our Histories: A Visual History of Black Lesbians in Post-Apartheid South Africa*, 2009, www.zanelemuholi.com, retrieved on 05 October 2010.
53. J. Nestle, C. Howell and R. Wilchins, *Gender Queer: Voices from Beyond the Sexual Binary*, Los Angeles: Alyson, 2002.
54. J. P. Paul, J. Cantania, L. Pollack, J. Moskowitz, J. Canchola, T. Mills, "Suicide attempts among gay and bisexual men: Lifetime prevalence and antecedents", *American Journal of Public Health*, 92, (8), 2002, pp. 1338–1345.
55. Phillips, "What's wrong with essentialism?", *Distinction: Scandinavian Journal of Social Theory*, 11, 2010, pp. 47–60.
56. N. Quinn, and W. Luttrell, "Psychodynamic universals, cultural particulars in feminist anthropology: Rethinking gender beliefs", *Ethos*, 32, 2004, pp. 493–513.
57. Rigmor C. Berg, H.M. Munthe-K and M.W. Ross, "Internalized Homonegativity: A Systematic Mapping Review of Empirical Research", *Journal of Homosexuality*, 63(4), 2016, pp. 541–558.
58. C.L. Ridgeway and S.J. Correll, Unpacking the gender system: A theoretical perspective on gender beliefs and social relations, *Gender and Society*, 18, 2004, pp. 510–531.
59. N. Riseman, "Just Another Start to the Denigration of Anzac Day: Evolving Commemorations of LGBTI Military Service", *Australian Historical Studies*, 48 (1), 2017, pp. 35–51.
60. N. Riseman, R Shirleene and W. Graham, *Serving in Silence? Australian LGBT Servicemen and Women*, Sydney: New South, 2018.
61. A.M. Rosenthal, D. Sylva, A. Safron and J.M. Bailey, "Sexual arousal patterns of bisexual men revisited", *Biological Psychology*, 88, 2011, pp. 112–115.
62. M.W. Ross, D.J. Smolenski, P. Kajubi, J.S. Mandel, W. McFarland, and F.H. Raymond, "Measurement of internalized homonegativity in gay and bisexual men in Uganda: Cross-cultural properties of the internalized homonegativity scale", *Psychology, Health & Medicine*, 15, 2010, pp. 159–165.
63. G. Rubin, "The Traffic in Women: Notes on the 'Political Economy' of Sex" in *Deviations: A Gayle Rubin Reader*, Durham, NC: Duke University Press, 2011, pp. 33–65.
64. G.M. Russell, "Internalized homophobia: Lessons from the Mobius strip", in C. Brown and T. Augusta-Scott (Eds.), *Narrative Therapy: Making meaning, making lives*, Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage 2007, pp. 151–173.
65. G.M. Russell and J.S. Bohan, "The case of internalized homophobia: Theory and practice", *Theory & Psychology*, 16, 2006, pp. 343–366.
66. C. Ryan, D. Huebner, R. Diaz, and J. Sanchez, "Family rejection as a predictor of negative health outcomes in White and Latino LGB young adults", *Pediatrics*, 123, 2009, pp. 346–352.
67. E.M. Saewyc, N. Singh, E. Reis, and T. Flynn, "The intersections of racial, gender and orientation harassment in school and health risk behaviors among adolescents", *Journal of Adolescent Health*, 26, 2000, p. 148.
68. S. Sanders, "Tackling homophobia, creating safer spaces", in R. dePalma and E. Atkinson (Eds.), *Invisible boundaries: Addressing sexualities equality in children's worlds*, Stoke-on-Trent, UK: Trentham, 2008, pp. 3–12.
69. R.L. Sell, "Defining and measuring sexual orientation: A review. Archives of Sexual Behavior", 26(6), 1997, pp. 643–657.
 A. Shidlo, "Internalized homophobia: Conceptual and empirical issues in measurement", in B. Green and G.M. Herek (Eds.), *Lesbian and gay psychology: Theory, research and clinical applications*, Thousand Oaks, CA: Sage, 1994, pp. 176–205.

70. R. Stall, T.C. Mills, J. Williamson, T. Hart, G. Greenwood, J.P. Paul, et al., "Association of co-occurring psychosocial health problems and increased vulnerability to HIV/AIDS among urban men who have sex with men", *American Journal of Public Health*, 93(6), 2003, pp. 939–942.
71. D.M. Szymanski, and E.R. Carr, "The roles of gender role conflict and internalized heterosexism in gay and bisexual men's psychological distress: Testing two mediation models", *Psychology of Men & Masculinity*, 9, 2008, pp. 40–54.
72. Msiibi Thabo, "The Lies We Have Been Told: On (Homo) Sexuality in Africa," *Africa Today*, 58, no. 1, 2011, pp. 55–77.
73. Thabo Msibi, "Is Current Theorising on Same-Sex Sexuality Relevant to the African Context? The Need for More African Voices on Theorising Same-Sex Desire in Africa," *Pambazo News*, 2014.
74. J.B. Tucker and H.H.J. Keil, "Can cultural beliefs cause a gender identity disorder?", *Journal of Psychology and Human Sexuality*, 13, 2001, 21–30.
75. G. Weinberg, *Society and the healthy homosexual*, Garden City, NY: Anchor Books, 1973.
76. S. Whittle, L. Turner and M. Al-Alami, "Endangered Penalties: Transgender and transsexual people's experiences of inequality and discrimination", *The Equality Review*, 2007, retrieved on 19 November 2010, from <http://www.pfc.org.uk/files/EndangeredPenalties.pdf>.